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THE THEME OF VICTORY IN THE WORK OF AZERBAIJANI ARTISTS LIVING ABROAD

Abstract. Undoubtedly, the victory won as a result of the 44-day war became a guarantee of high spirits, interesting works were created on topics glorifying the military power of the state and the corresponding victory, war heroes and martyrs. The article analyzes the works of artists living abroad – in Germany, Turkey, Georgia, draws attention to the semantic and content component of the works. In our opinion, the creation of wonderful works that will reflect the immeasurable significance of this historic victory is still ahead.

Key words: Victory, Karabakh, artist, soldier, war.

Introduction. Undoubtedly, the victory won as a result of the 44-day war became a guarantee of high spirits, interesting works were created on topics glorifying the military power of the state and the corresponding victory, war heroes and martyrs. In the article, works related to this topic in the works of artists living abroad are brought to attention.

The interpretation of the main material. The artist we would like to talk about first is Ashraf Heybatov, who currently lives in Koblenz, Germany. After some time, while living in Moscow, Tahir Salahov provided spiritual support to his creativity.

Addressing various genres, the artist glorifies the nature, history, culture, folklore and traditions of Azerbaijan in his works. Both Eastern and Western themes can be seen in his works.

As soon as the second Karabakh war began, he began to work on the triptych “Victory celebration in Karabakh”, which is 1.5 meters

high and 3 meters long. He brought it to Baku and presented it in the Central Officers' House named after Hazi Aslanov. Military school cadets and intellectuals came to the presentation and donated his work to the Ministry of Defense. The work is kept in the Ministry's Military Museum (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Ashraf Heybatov. “Victory celebration in Karabakh”, 2020.

In the center of the composition we see the image of a soldier holding a gun and a flag. At the same time, elements related to Azerbaijani culture and art are mentioned in the work, and the expression of the fighting spirit of the Azerbaijani army can be felt. Due to its artistic solution, this work, which expresses the people's will and struggle with high craftsmanship, can also be considered a monumental panel.

Another artist, Muhammad Aliyev, who moved to the brotherly country in 1996, is currently continuing his teaching activities at Gaziantep University, sharing the secrets of his art with the younger generations.

For information, let's note that Muhammad Aliyev was born in Baku in 1952 and completed his secondary education in his native country. He graduated from the Baku Art School named after Azim Azimzadeh (1968-1973) and studied at the branch of the Leningrad (St. Petersburg) Higher Art

School named after V. Mukhina (1978-1983). His first solo exhibition was in 1985 in Saint Petersburg.

In 1986, Muhammad Aliyev was elected a member of the Union of Artists of the USSR. In the bloody days of January 1990, the painting “Voice of Souls” was hung on the Baku metro as a sign of protest against what happened. In 1991, the St. Petersburg State Museum bought his painting “Lovers” at a high price. After moving to Turkey and starting to live here, his works became more interesting. In the shortest time, his paintings were exhibited in the USA, England, Austria, Germany and France, and brought fame to the author with his modernist style. He is a painter, sculptor, ceramist and graphic artist. After he started living in Turkey, his exhibition was opened only once in Azerbaijan, in the fall of 2007. About 60 works of the artist were presented at the exhibition organized at the Central Exhibition Hall named after Sattar Bahlulzade. He is known as “Turkey’s Picasso” [1, p. 16].

His works in the genres of oil painting, ceramics, and graphics have been exhibited in exhibitions in Azerbaijan, Russia, Turkey, USA, England, Austria, Germany, France and other countries since the 90s of the last century.

Muhammad Aliyev has prepared a new collection dedicated to the historic Victory in the 44-day Patriotic War. The paintings included in the collection reflect subjects such as the Victorious Commander-in-Chief of Azerbaijan, our Invincible Army, the devotion of our people to the motherland and land, and the great role played by our religious and linguistic unity in our holy victory.

The solo exhibition of the artist, whose 70th anniversary will be completed in 2022, was opened in Gaziantep, Turkey. The exhibition “60 years in art” organized in the gallery of the Academy of Arts was met with great interest.

In the composition “Sound of azan after 28 years in Shusha”, shown in the exhibition, we see soldiers praying, hanging the flag of Azerbaijan on the minarets of the Govharaga Mosque in Shusha, laying down their weapons. In this way, the artist paid tribute to the memory of our martyrs who had a great role in winning the Victory (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Muhammad Aliyev. "Sound of azan after 28 years in Shusha", 2020.

He considers himself lucky and happy that he is living these glorious days of victory and intends to devote his future work to the themes of victory.

One of our artists working outside our country is the well-known artist Mansur Jafarov. The artist working in Turkey was born in 1957 in Dasta village of Ordubad district of Nakhchivan MR.

He studied at the Azerbaijan State Art School named after A. Azimzade, the academic painting faculty of the Azerbaijan State University of Culture and Arts. In 1997-2001, he taught painting at the university. He has been a member of the Union of Azerbaijan Artists since 1997, and a member of the Black Sea Plastic Arts Union since 2008. Since 2007, he has been working as a docent-doctor in the Faculty of Fine Arts, Trabzon Black Sea Technical University, Turkey.

Mansur Jafarov says that he teaches painting at the university where he works, just like in Azerbaijan: “A very strong tradition of professional painting has been formed in Azerbaijan, and valuable artists have grown up. I am now teaching my experience there to Turkish students. Every artist should know the academic rules. There are many promising students” [2].

The author’s joy of victory can be clearly felt in the artistic capacity of the artist’s work “Victory Celebration”, which is compact but has a deep content.

In the composition created in mixed technique, sangina, measuring 25x35 cm, we can see the faces of soldiers looking to the right and left, and in the center, a person who is sitting and playing the ney. We even see the birds joining in the joy of the soldiers (fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Mansur Jafarov. “Victory Celebration”, 2022.

Elshan Sarkhanoglu is one of our artists who continues his creative activity in Antalya, Turkey. He graduated from the art school and then the art faculty of the Azerbaijan State University of Culture and Arts. He is a member of the Union of Azerbaijan Artists and the Union of Theater Workers of Azerbaijan. His works are stored in 22 museums in our country and around the world, he has staged more than 50 performances and is a laureate of a number of painting competitions.

The “Victory” painting created by him on the subject is divided into 3 parts in the colors of the Azerbaijani flag. White birds, a symbol of peace, are flying in the blue sky (a sign that Azerbaijan is a peaceful country). In the middle part, those peace-loving birds - in the green part below, they pounce on enemy equipment that has penetrated our land. The red-colored birds were our martyrs, a sign of defeating the enemy at the cost of their blood and lives. On the right side of the painting, below, in black color, the destroyed enemy equipment is shown in a state that has been compressed and removed from the painting (our land). Also, the enemy’s equipment is in the form of a threat extending towards our land. In the right part of the painting, above, after liberating the land, prosperous peace birds fly again (a sign of the immortal souls of our martyrs) (fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Elshan Sarkhanoglu, “Victory”.

The meaning-content load achieved by the author with the contrasts of form and color is quite attractive and effective.

One of the artists we would like to talk about is Rizvan Ismayil, who lives and works in Georgia. He was born in 1969 in the village of Zveli-Kveshi, Bolnisi region, Georgia. He studied at the Azerbaijan State Art School named

after A. Azimzadeh in 1986-1990. Since 2007, the artist has participated in individual and group exhibitions in Tbilisi, Istanbul, Brussels, Luxembourg, Baku, Paris (Carousel du Louvre) and Moscow. His works adorn private collections and galleries. Rizvan Ismail became a member of the Federation of Georgian Artists in 2015, a member of the Azerbaijan Advertisers Union in 2016, the head of the Georgian office of this union, and was elected a member of the Georgian Artists Union in 2017. In 2016, the artist was awarded the “Friendship of Peoples” order of the Turkic world.

He is one of the founders of the new “Numerologism” (Abjadism) style applied in painting, sculpture and architecture [3].

Numerology is an esoteric (hidden) belief system about the existence of mysterious relationships of physical objects, processes, human life and consciousness, with mutual relations and counter-effects of numbers.

The artist contributed to the 44-day Victory of Azerbaijan, the restoration of territories freed from occupation, as well as its promotion.

His work, developed in Abjadism style, is called “44 steps of victory”. The road to victory, determination to ensure victory, as well as patriotism are reflected in the composition made with oil paint on canvas. Fragmented pomegranate seeds and nightingale are also depicted in the work (fig. 5).

One of the commendable works on the subject was created by the talented young artist Tahmina Ali.

For information, let’s note that Tahmina Ali was born in 1986 in Tivi village of Ordubad region. He moved to

Fig. 5. Rizvan Ismayil. “44 steps of victory”, 2022.

Baku in 1993. Since he had a great passion for painting since childhood, in 2005 he was admitted to the “graphics” department of the “Fine Art” faculty of the Azerbaijan State Academy of Arts. During his student years, he participated in national and international exhibitions. In 2006, for his active participation in the caricature exhibition of the Union of Cartoonists of Azerbaijan, he was awarded a membership card of that union and the Union of Azerbaijan Artists.

Since 2017, he has participated in a number of local and international exhibitions, starting his artistic activity in Ankara, Turkey.

In 2019, he participated in the art exhibition “Peak of Development” with his work “Victory Celebration”. Before long, this painting, which consists of the artist’s thoughts, becomes a reality. The artist remembers those moments like this:

- “With this painting, I wanted to revive our heroic Army behind our President, our national leader Heydar Aliyev, who laid the foundations of the road to our glorious Victory, and our brave men who died for Karabakh. At the same time, the work glorifies the freedom of Karabakh and Shusha. I tried to express the joy of Victory in my heart with this work” (fig. 6).

Conclusion. Today’s victory is the peak event - the brightest page in the history of our nation’s rich and glorious statehood during the period of independence. This is an exceptional political event and a Victory epic that has no parallel in the history of our statehood.

It is commendable that the spiritual burden of the Karabakh war, which gives

Fig. 6. Tahmina Ali.
“Victory Celebration”, 2019.

pride to each of us, is reflected in the examples of art these days. In our opinion, the creation of wonderful works that will reflect the immeasurable significance of this historic victory is still ahead...

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Ramil Quliyev (Azərbaycan)

XARİCDƏ YAŞAYAN AZƏRBAYCAN RƏSSAMLARIN YARADICILIGINDA “ZƏFƏR” MÖVZUSU

Şübhəsiz ki, 44 günlük müharibə nəticəsində qazanılan “Zəfər” böyük ruh yüksəkliyinə səbəb olmuş, dövlətin hərbi qüdrətini tərənnüm edən mövzulara və ona uyğun gələn “Zəfər”ə, müharibə qəhrəmanlarına, şəhidlərə həsr olunmuş maraqlı əsərlər yaradılmışdır. Məqalədə, xaricdə - Almaniya, Türkiyə, Gürcüstanda yaşayan rəssamların yaradıcılığında bu mövzu ilə bağlı olan əsərlər təhlil edilərək məna-məzmun yükü diqqətə çatdırılmışdır. Qənaətimizcə, bu tarixi qələbənin ölçüyəgəlməzliyini özündə hifz edəcək möhtəşəm əsərlərin yaradılması isə hələ qabaqdadır.

Açar sözlər: Zəfər, Qarabağ, rəssam, əsgər, müharibə.

Рамиль Гулиев (Азербайджан)

ТЕМА ПОБЕДЫ В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКИХ ХУДОЖНИКОВ, ЖИВУЩИХ ЗА РУБЕЖОМ

Несомненно, одержанная в результате 44-дневной войны победа стала залогом приподнятого настроения, были созданы интересные произведения, посвященные темам, прославляющим военную мощь государства и соответствующую этому победу, героев войны и шахидов. В статье анализируются произведения художников, проживающих за границей – в Германии, Турции, Грузии, обращается внимание на смысловое содержание этих работ. На наш взгляд, создание замечательных произведений, которые будут отражать неизмеримость значения этой исторической победы, еще впереди.

Ключевые слова: Победа, Карабах, художник, солдат, война.